

PARTIAL RECONFIGURATION FOR SIGNAL PROCESSING APPLICATION USING FPGA

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ABSTRACT

DSP Application needs to speed-up in computation time can be achieved by assigning complex computation intensive tasks to hardware and by exploiting the parallelism in algorithms. These applications need high performance as well as cost efficient design. Reconfigurable systems offer us potential for computation acceleration due to its software-like programmable nature of the parallel processing units. Run-time configuration explores a novel research area for reconfigurable hardware to further speedup the processing speed by eliminating the configuration overhead with the overlapping of execution time. Dynamic partial reconfigurable FPGAs offer new design space with a variety of benefits: reduce the configuration time and save memory as the partial reconfiguration files (bit-streams) are smaller than full ones. This paper introduces a simple reconfigurable system and focuses on the newest dynamic partial reconfiguration design flow.

KEYWORDS: Partial Reconfiguration, DSP, FPGA

I. INTRODUCTION

In DSP applications computation intensive algorithms used in image and signal processing, multimedia, telecommunications, cryptography, networking and computation domains in general were first realized using software running on Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) or General Purpose Processors (GPPs). Significant speed-up in computation time can be achieved by assigning complex Computation intensive tasks to hardware and by exploiting the parallelism in algorithms. Matrix multiplication is the kernel operation used in many image and signal processing applications. The designs are optimized for speed which is the main requirement in these applications. The (FPGA) market growing. Their great advantage is their flexibility that arises from their programmable nature as compared to systems using application specific integrated circuits (ASICs). There is a new concept evolving in FPGA industry. The so-called dynamic partial reconfiguration (DPR) can be exploited in many application fields, for instance to fulfill space requirements in small portable systems, to create a system-on-a-chip with a very high level of flexibility, to realize adaptive hardware algorithms, and so on.

II. DYNAMIC PR

Partial reconfiguration (PR) is the ability to reconfigure select areas of an FPGA any time after its initial reconfiguration

2.1. Two groups of PR

From the functionality of the design, partial reconfiguration can be dinto two groups: dynamic partial reconfiguration (DPR) and static partial reconfiguration. Dynamic partial reconfiguration, which is illustrated in figure1, also known as active partial reconfiguration, permits to

change a part of the device while the rest of an FPGA is still running. In static partial reconfiguration the device is not active during the reconfiguration process. In other words, while the partial data is sent into the FPGA, the rest of the device is stopped and brought up after the configuration is completed. Dynamic partial reconfiguration is carried out to allow the FPGA to adapt to changing hardware algorithms, improve fault tolerance and resource utilization, to enhance Performance or to reduce power consumption. DPR is especially valuable where devices operate in a mission critical environment that cannot be disrupted while some subsystems are being redefined. DPR is not supported on all FPGAs. The Xilinx FPGAs (i.e. Virtex series) are some of the few devices on the market allowing dynamic partial reconfiguration

Figure 1. Dynamic partial reconfiguration

2.2. Several styles DPR

Xilinx inc. suggests in [2] two basic styles of dynamic reconfiguration on a single FPGA: the Difference-based partial reconfiguration and the module-based partial reconfiguration. Difference-based partial reconfiguration can be used when a small change is made to the design. It is especially useful in case of changing Look-Up Table (LUT) equations or dedicated memory blocks content. The partial bit-stream contains only information about differences between the current design structure (that resides in the FPGA) and the new content of an FPGA. Switching the configuration of a module from one implementation to another is very quick, as the bit-stream differences can be extremely smaller than the entire device bit-stream. Module-based partial reconfiguration uses modular design concepts to reconfigure large blocks of logic. The distinct portions of the design to be reconfigured are known as reconfigurable modules. Because specific properties and specific layout criteria must be met with respect to a reconfigurable module, any FPGA design intending to use partial reconfiguration must be planned and laid out with that in mind.

Figure 2. Static partial reconfiguration

III. DESIGN FLOW USING PLAN AHEAD

Partial Reconfiguration in ISE 11 uses a bottom-up synthesis with top-down implementation methodology. This particular design and tutorial uses XST to synthesize the design and Plan Ahead as the implementation environment. Other tools and methodologies may be used to successfully implement a Partial Reconfiguration design

Figure 3. Design Steps

IV. RECONFIGURABLE FIR FILTER DESIGN

The FIR filter computes an output from a set of input Samples, which is multiplied by a set of coefficients. And then the FIR filter adds together to produce the output. Implementation of FIR filters can be undertaken in either hardware or software. A software implementation will require sequential execution of the filter functions. Hardware implementation of FIR filters allows the filter functions to be executed in a parallel manner, which makes improved filter processing speed as fast as possible but is less flexible for changes. Thus, reconfigurable FIR filter offers both the flexibility of computer software, and the ability to construct Custom high performance computing circuits. Fig. 5 shows the partial reconfigurable n-order FIR filter, which can implement from $n=8$ to 20

V. IMPLEMENTATION

On adaptive systems, a limited factor for the overall system Performance is often the speed of which the system is able to adapt to perform a certain task. This section describes the Implementation method of 20-tap FIR filter, which can Reconfigured partially from 8-tap to maximum 20-tap FIR filter. The whole system is implemented on a Xilinx Virtex-4 FPGA

A. HDL design description and Synthesis

Partial reconfiguration requires a hierarchical design approach that must be strictly followed during the HDL coding process. The first step of the PR design flow is to define 3kinds of HDL design description and then synthesize those HDL descriptions separately. These HDL design descriptions are composed to following three design modules.

* Top-level design module:

In this step, we must consider each sub-module interconnection using bus macro and area assignment. Top-level description must only contain I/O, Clock primitive, Base design, PR module, bus-macro instantiations and signal declarations.

* Base design module:

Base design module is static design module which means that base design module will not reconfigure even if partial reconfiguration is performed. Therefore, this step is same to traditional HDL design method. But designer must consider input and output assign rule for partial reconfiguration.

* PR design module:

PR module is also same to traditional HDL design method. However PR module can exist two or more. Therefore designer must describe multiple description of HDL.

B. Set Design Constrains

After the HDL design description is synthesized, the next step is to place constraint on the design for place and route (PAR) and timing constraint to improve the design performance. Design constraints must have area group, reconfiguration mode and bus macro location constraints.

C. Implement Base Design

First, the base design must be implemented. The information generated by implement base design is used for partial reconfigurable modules implementation phase.

D. Implement Partial Reconfigurable Modules

After the base design is implemented, each PR modules must also be implemented. Each of the PR modules must be implemented separately.

E. Merge

The final step in the PR design flow is to merge the top, base, and PR modules. During the merge step, a complete design is built from each PRM and the base design. In this step, many partial bit-streams for each PRM and initial full bit streams are created to configure the FPGA.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a reconfigurable FIR filter design using dynamic partial reconfiguration, which has area efficiency, flexibility and configuration time advantage allowing dynamically inserting and/or removing the partial modules. The proposed method produces a reduction in hardware cost and allows performing partial reconfiguration, where a reduced bit-stream reconfigures only a given subset of internal components.

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